

Fast Growth and Slow Policy: A Decade of Digital Credit in Kenya

Rafe Mazer & Seth Garz

Draft of August 11, 2023

Abstract

The proliferation of mobile enabled instant credit products (digital credit) across emerging markets and developing economies poses challenges for policymakers and practitioners that seek to expand access to credit while protecting consumers. The Kenya market, which experienced tremendous commercial innovation and growth from 2012-2022, but also significant consumer harms and unequal competition, offers a valuable reference case for actors in other markets facing rapid expansion of new fintech products and firms. Despite the substantial and often polarized debate around the country's experience, there has been little systematic effort to capture and interpret key facts from the development of the digital credit market in Kenya during its first decade. This paper aims to fill that gap by providing a policy case study informed by original interviews of key stakeholders and extensive review of related academic and grey literature. The analysis suggests that policy responses were often inadequate to address the growing risks in Kenya's digital credit market and presents five policy reflections from Kenya's experience to support consumer protection and competition in emerging digital credit markets.

Introduction

In 2012 Kenya's first digital credit product, M-Shwari, was launched by Safaricom and the Commercial Bank of Africa. Just two years later M-Shwari had already disbursed more than 20 million loans. Not only was this product incredibly popular, but it also profoundly transformed the borrowing experience by enabling consumers to quickly apply for micro-loans on basic mobile phones and to receive near-instant underwriting responses from the lender. This transformation was particularly acute for those that did not previously have access to formal loans, but were now eligible for digital credit. Those with access to loans grew from 58% of adults in 2013 to 74% in 2021 driven in large part by digital credit ([FSD Kenya, 2021](#)). Such dramatic financial innovation may have been surprising in a country of sub-US\$1,500 GDP per capita ([World Bank, n.d.](#)) were it not for Kenya's high rate of mobile money adoption and the digital infrastructure of Kenya's dominant vertically integrated mobile network operator and mobile money provider, Safaricom.

Upon these "digital financial rails," digital credit quickly evolved from a commercial pilot to a pillar of Kenya's economic policy. In November 2022, exactly ten years after the introduction of digital credit, the Government of Kenya launched the Hustler Fund as a signature small enterprise development program of President William Ruto's new administration. Through digital credit loans paid out via mobile money, the Hustler Fund distributed around US\$200 million in just its first four months ([Kinyanjui, 2023](#)), with the policy goal "to make affordable credit to sections of the population that have been left behind for far too long ([Hustler Fund, n.d.](#))."

The first decade of digital credit, however, was not just a celebration of achieving massive scale in lending. As digital credit expanded both in new borrowers and in the imagination of policymakers, the financial wellbeing of Kenyans declined, raising skepticism about the virtues of digital credit. The fraction of “financially healthy adults” declined from 39% in 2016 to 22% in 2019 to just 17% in 2021 with digital credit products experiencing the highest rate of default among any loan products ([FDS Kenya, 2021](#)). Complementing this descriptive *association* between the parallel rise of digital credit and decline in financial health, a cluster of evidence from rigorous evaluations in Kenya and other regions documents little to no average *causal impacts* of digital credit on key human development indicators ([Robinson et al., 2022](#)). Furthermore, reports have documented the abundance of consumer harms and anti-competitive practices in the digital credit sector, many of which are described in detail below.

From commercial pilot to economic pillar, the policy journey of the first decade of digital credit in Kenya offers important lessons for countries contemplating how to engage the opportunities and potential perils of digital credit and related digital financial technologies. Notwithstanding digital credit’s commercial success, the limited evidence of impact and abundant documentation of harm from the form of digital credit that has proliferated in Kenya beg key policy questions. How can emerging markets and developing economies mobilize sufficient regulatory resources in time to effectively respond to a fast-growing digital financial services sector? Where and when is the value of digital credit and related financial products sufficient to justify unsupervised growth that exposes many citizens to consumer protection harms? If the impacts of digital credit are modest, then the ability of regulators to guard against the downside consequences becomes more urgent.

This paper documents and interprets the ten year policy journey of digital credit in Kenya, capturing key policy lessons relevant for other markets. The paper draws on academic literature and grey literature from practitioners, government, and media, and original interviews with more than 20 donors, investors, financial service providers, policymakers, and researchers involved in Kenya’s digital credit journey. Five priority policy reflections emerged from this analysis and are the subject of extended discussion throughout this report:

1. **Do not delay in formalizing rules after enabling innovation.** While permission to pilot digital credit innovations was granted in a clear and timely manner to some banks, rules regarding digital lending overall were not formalized until a decade after digital credit came to Kenya, leaving little supervision or consumer protection for many digital credit customers.
2. **Consumer protection matters and needs to be addressed early on.** The lack of action on market conduct and consumer protection for many years had real consequences for Kenyan financial consumers. These experiences speak to the importance of having proper market coverage and conduct mandates in place early, to avoid imposing different levels of protection for the same product types.
3. **Credit reference bureaus and data sharing rules must keep pace with digital innovation.** Kenya’s experience demonstrates that inconsistently and poorly enforced loan reporting requirements can undermine competition and harm consumers. Even ten years into digital credit, Kenya’s credit reference bureau (CRB) rules remain behind the digital times with lenders only required to report loans at the end of the month, a timeframe that is out of line with the fast pace of digital loan decisioning. The period of 2020 to 2022 saw a range of policy actions related to credit reporting,

including removal of non-bank digital lenders from the credit information systems, expunging of millions of loan records, and the introduction of a credit repair framework policy; however, wholesale reforms to reporting requirements and more forceful supervision remain underdeveloped.

4. **Robust investment in policy architecture and supervisory staffing is needed for proper market monitoring.** As consumer protection risks arose in digital credit, the lack of a consumer protection and market conduct authority hindered policy response. There were two separate attempts to introduce such an authority in 2016 and 2018, which were opposed by financial sector regulators and subsequently abandoned. At the same time, there is still a lack of dedicated fintech and consumer protection departments in financial sector regulators, and insufficient staffing to supervise digital credit. This hinders the government’s ability to act on consumer protection abuses and has delayed the licensing process for digital credit providers.
5. **Digital credit requires robust pro-competition policy.** Kenya is home to a highly concentrated mobile payments and digital credit market. Safaricom’s M-PESA accounts for 97% of total mobile money volumes, and the two digital lenders on M-PESA’s platform—NCBA and Kenya Commercial Bank (KCB)—account for 95% of digital credit volumes. The fast-scaling nature of digital credit, as well as the ability to leverage dominance in telecommunications or payments to achieve market dominance in digital credit, requires addressing competition issues to ensure robust price-based competition and to enable consumers to easily switch providers without losing benefits such as credit history or loan limits.

Each of these reflections is discussed in more detail below. The paper then concludes with forward-looking lessons, so that the next generation of digital credit may better deliver on the promise and potential envisioned when the first products were launched a decade ago.

Defining “Digital Credit”

This paper is principally focused on the growth and regulation of loans delivered via phones with near instantaneous algorithm-driven underwriting decisioning, for which funding and repayment are facilitated via digital payment systems (“mobile money”). In Kenya, as further discussed below, these loans tend to be small (average loan size of 5,962 Kenyan shillings - approximately \$42) and short-term (30-60 days), or to take the form of a mobile money payments account overdraft facility ([Gubbins, 2019](#)). Data suggest these loans are more likely to be used for consumption than production purposes ([Blackmon et al., 2021](#)), though this distinction may not be so crisp for a low-income household for which informal entrepreneurship often necessitates merging household and “enterprise” balance sheets.

Lenders distributing these small instant short-term loans employ a variety of different business and underwriting models. However, a few key business innovations are often associated with digital credit. In particular, loans are unsecured, but borrowers begin with small micro-loans that escalate in size conditional on positive repayment behavior, creating a dynamic incentive to repay. Lenders may access mobile money transaction data along with other “non-traditional” sources of data accessible on consumer’s mobile phones or associated with their personal identifiers to inform their underwriting decisions, which are automated by machine-driven algorithms.

To avoid confusion, we refer herein to these loan products with the commonly used term “digital credit,” but support the use of more specific terminology of “mobile-enabled instant credit” (MIC) that has been suggested elsewhere ([IPA and CEGA, forthcoming](#)). The greater specificity in terminology is increasingly important given the broader trend towards digitization of all kinds of formerly analog debt products and the creation of new debt products that would not have been feasible before the broad adoption of digital payments systems and associated new consumer and producer use cases. While this paper remains focused on small-value mobile-enabled instant “digital credit,” many of the policy insights derived from the Kenya experience should be relevant for other emerging forms of digital lending within and outside of the Kenya market.

Methodology

This paper aims to provide a policy case study that captures and interprets key facts from the development of the digital credit market informed by original interviews of key stakeholders and extensive review of academic and grey literature research.

Our initial sample of interview respondents was identified based on the authors’ professional experiences working with donors, research organizations, and civil society groups in the digital finance sector. The sample then snowballed based on recommendations and referrals from the original set of respondents to include a total of 24 interviews with individuals from 10 research or policy making institutions, 11 commercial providers, and 3 philanthropic or public funders. Given the small community of practitioners working in or with the Kenya market, we have avoided attributing opinions or quotations even anonymously; though, respondents were informed of and consented to the use of content from their interviews in this publication. Notably, a handful of key stakeholders declined to participate.

In addition to conforming to a semi-structured rubric of questions, the interviews included what is to our understanding a novel “sorting milestones” method for identifying key historic events in the evolution of the Kenyan digital credit market and for soliciting critical policy analysis and counterfactual policy recommendations from respondents. For the “sorting milestones” exercise, respondents reviewed a list of key milestones in digital credit in Kenya and were asked to conduct the following tasks: i) add events to the list, ii) select up to five positive and five negative events, and iii) select up to three events of which they would change the outcome and share the alternative decision, intervention, policy, etc. they would have recommended. We “seeded” the list of milestones based on our own prior beliefs about key events, adding new events that were mentioned by the interviewees (new additions are identified in italics in Table 1).

We designed the “sorting milestones” method to overcome shortcomings of other qualitative approaches to reconstructing historical timelines. First, we wanted to reduce the risk of excluding key events and, therefore, invited respondents to add events that were not included in the initial timeline we seeded based on our own experience and literature review. Second, we wanted to minimize the risk of over-emphasizing events that were less consequential – a sort of false positive – by having respondents weigh the importance of the events. Third, we wanted to systematically compel respondents to apply positive or negative valence to key events to discipline our interpretation of the less structured content of the interviews and our interpretation of how widespread beliefs were about the positive or negative impacts

of any given event. Fourth, we wanted to illustrate a set of counterfactual outcomes to the true historical experience guided by a set of feasible alternative decisions, interventions, and/or policies.

Description of the Crowded but Concentrated Kenya Digital Credit Market

Kenya's digital credit market is both crowded and concentrated. While hundreds of existing and new lenders applied for the new digital credit provider (DCP) license in 2022, the overwhelming majority of the loan volume in digital credit is from KCB and NCBA, the two banks partnering with Safaricom to offer the Fuliza overdraft facility and digital loans through the M-PESA platform. Analysis from MicroSave Consulting finds that "Safaricom processes 95% of all digital loans." As of March 2022, Fuliza counted with 2 million active *daily* users, and KCB M-PESA and M-Shwari counted with 3.8 million and 4.7 million *monthly* active users, respectively.¹ To understand how this compares with non-bank digital lenders, the Competition Authority of Kenya (CAK)'s *Digital Credit Market Inquiry* compared the total value of loans disbursed each month by these three loan products and three other providers (See Figure 1). This sample included one of the larger non-bank lenders and some noteworthy bank digital lenders; yet, the three Safaricom-linked lenders (F, H1 and H2 in Figure 1) far surpassed the volumes of any of the other lenders in the sample.

The high concentration of digital lending associated with Safaricom is a key distinguishing feature of the Kenyan market and reflects the company's vertical integration paired with near perfect monopoly-level dominance in mobile money. Safaricom accounts for 95% of mobile money volumes in Kenya, in addition to which the company provides telecommunications infrastructure and services, and now digital lending and savings products. Consistent with literature on the political economy of banking regulation ([Avgouleas et al, 2019](#)), the Kenyan market structure may explain some of the slow regulatory response to consumer protection issues discussed below.

¹ Internal analysis provided by MicroSave Consulting. March, 2023.

Figure 1: Value of Digital Loan Disbursements among Large Kenyan Lenders (Reproduced with permission from Putman, et al 2021)

What were key milestones in Kenya’s digital credit journey?

Interviewees for this report reviewed a list of key milestones in digital credit in Kenya and were asked to conduct several tasks: 1. Add events to the list (additions from interviewees are in *italics*), 2. Select up to five positive and five negative events; and 3. Select up to three events of which they would change the outcome. Below is a summary of the respondents’ votes, and some comments from their choices. The five most common “positive,” “negative,” and “change outcome” milestones are highlighted.

Among the most common negative milestones identified were the Central Bank of Kenya’s moratorium on negative credit bureau listing issued during the beginning of the Covid epidemic in 2020, the bank interest rate cap policy adopted in 2016, the launch of Safaricom’s Fuliza overdraft facility in 2019, the court ruling that CBA-Safaricom’s M-Shwari loans did not have to comply with interest rate caps in 2018, and the launch of the Hustler Fund in 2022. Notably, these milestones receive few to no positive votes. Despite the negativity associated with the launch of the digital credit products with Fuliza and the Hustler Fund, there are seven positive votes for the M-Shwari product launch in 2012, suggesting respondents by no means take a binary view of all digital credit products as negative. The M-Shwari launch is second only to support for the launch of M-PESA in 2007 in positive votes received. On the launch of the Hustler Fund, respondents were divided with one commenting that the fund should not have been launched and another commenting that the fund was a great idea that was poorly executed. Similarly, the negative characterization of various regulatory interventions does not reflect some sort of universal bias against regulatory intervention, as the CAK adoption of price transparency rules in 2016 and Data Protection Act of 2019 receive five and six positive votes respectively and no negative votes.

Many of the milestones for which respondents voted to “change outcome” reflect regulations or rulings that unequally applied to some lenders and not others, such as the interest rate cap exception granted to M-Shwari that, as one voter said, “showed rules applied differently dependent on political power.” Notably, with seven “change outcome votes,” respondents unambiguously lamented the failure to pass the Draft Financial Market Conduct Authority Bill published by Treasury in 2018, which one participant

described as a “law that reflects lender diversity and removes industry silos.” This theme of the importance in developing and applying regulations across all providers and the need to foster fair competition emerged not only in this sorting milestones exercise, but also in the extended interviews.

Table 1: Key Milestones in Kenya’s Digital Credit Policy Journey

Year	Milestone	Positive	Negative	Change Outcome	Sample of suggested changes and key concerns
2007	M-PESA mobile money service launched (Vodafone, 2017)	9	0	1	*Put the regulations in writing immediately, and prohibit things like exclusivity from the beginning.
2008	Regulations for credit reference bureaus (CRBs) issued (Kenya Law, 2018)	4	0	4	*Should have put oversight of the CRBs under a different regulator. *Written with banks in mind, not reflective of digital lenders.
2012	M-Shwari digital credit product launched (Vodafone, 2017)	7	0	2	*Don’t allow exclusive partnerships with M-PESA platform *CRB and consumer protection policies should have been in place
2013	CRB regulations amended to allow third-party credit providers (Central Bank of Kenya, 2013)	4	0	2	*Allow data monetization for technology firms *Give CIS-K more enforcement powers, make it mandatory for third party credit providers to submit to the CRBs
2014	First non-bank FinTechs enter the digital credit market (Bock, 2016)	2	1	2	*Create a separate CIS framework outside traditional banking, with reporting of aggregate monthly usage for digital credit loans *Have more controls in place for non-bank digital lenders
2014	Equitel MVNO launch (Syminvest, 2014)	1	0	0	
2014	Legal Advice Center files case to block Equitel ThinSim rollout (Telecompaper, 2014)	0	3	0	
2015	KCB M-PESA digital credit product launched (Safaricom, n.d.)	2	0	0	
2016	CAK issues price transparency rules (Mazer, 2016)	5	0	0	

2016	M-Shwari reports positive loans to CRBs (Mazer et al., 2016²)	2	0	0	
2016	CAK caps wholesale USSD fees in DFS (Nkonjera, 2017 ; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2020)	4	0	0	
2016	Bank interest rate cap law (Central Bank of Kenya, 2016)	1	5	1	*Have the interest rate cap apply to all lenders not just banks
2017	MicroSave finds more than 2.7M negative mobile loans in CRB data (Mustafa et al, 2017)	1	3	1	*Don't negatively list these loans
2018	Court rules M-Shwari loans don't have to comply with interest rate cap (Guguyu, 2018)	1	4	3	*Ruling should have been that these loans were covered by the cap *Ruling showed rules applied differently dependent on political power
2018	Draft Financial Market Conduct Authority Bill published by Treasury (The National Treasury of Kenya, 2018)	0	1	7	*Need law that reflects lender diversity and removes industry silos *Have this bill put into law
2019	Digital Lenders Association of Kenya is formed (Financial Fortune Media, 2019)	6	0	0	
2018	Interest rate cap is repealed (Herbling et al., 2018)	2	2	0	
2019	Google issues rules for app store loans, including 60-day minimum loan term (Amadala, 2019)	1	2	0	
2019	FSDK FinAccess shows decline in financial health (Central Bank of Kenya, 2019)	2	2	1	*There was no discussion on why this happened and what policies could address the problem

² This report notes M-Shwari's non-compliance. Sources from CRBs confirmed they began complying soon after the report.

2019	FSDK study documents numerous fraudulent or low quality fintech apps (Gwer et al, 2019)	0	3	0	
2019	Fuliza M-PESA overdraft product launched, within a year is largest digital lender by volume and value (Safaricom, 2019)	1	5	3	*It should not have been exclusive to 2 banks *Make this only for MSMEs, not consumers
2019	Data Protection Act signed into law (Office of the Data Protection Commissioner in Kenya, 2019)	6	0	0	
2019	CBK partners with 5 banks for Stawi, a digital MSME loan facility (Owino, 2019)	0	2	2	*Don't do this program *Make it merchant financing
2019	DLAK issues member code of conduct (Mbego, 2019)	2	1	0	
2019	CRB template for mobile loans issued (Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya, 2019)	0	0	0	
2020	Moratorium on negative listings, removal of negative listings under Ksh1,000 and of non-bank digital lenders from CRB (Central Bank of Kenya, 2020)	2	7	1	
2020	Reports emerge of social shaming and other debt collection abuses by lenders (Kiruga, 2020)	1	4	0	
2020	Zero rating of mobile money transfer fees (Babatunde, 2020)	0	1	1	*Keep zero rating in place permanently
2021	CAK Digital Credit Market Inquiry (Putman et al., 2021)	0	1	1	*Take into consideration the policy recommendations made

2021	CBK Act modified to allow for regulation of digital lenders (Reuters, 2021)	2	0	1	
2021	Negative listings under Ksh5M removed from CRB (Central Bank of Kenya, 2021)	0	6	0	
2022	CBK issues digital credit regulations (Central Bank of Kenya, 2022)	3	3	2	*Issue the regulations sooner
2022	First non-bank digital lenders licenses issued (Nderi, 2022)	0	0	2	*Issue the licenses earlier *Go further to cover more types of non-bank lenders beyond digital
2022	Google issues new rules for Play Store, pledges to remove non-licensed lenders (CM Advocates LLP, 2023)	1	0	0	
2022	Credit Repair Framework issued (Central Bank of Kenya, 2022)	1	1	4	*This is not within regulator's jurisdiction *Instead of writing off debt develop a new repayment schedule *Include non-bank digital lenders in framework
2022	<i>Hustler Fund for micro-enterprise digital credit launched</i> (Reuters, 2022)	0	4	3	*Don't launch. Work with private sector to reduce cost of capital *Great idea, poorly executed
2023	<i>Start-up bill developed by government and industry representatives</i> (Kenya Moja, 2022)	0	0	1	*Have this passed into law

Reflection #1: Do not delay in formalizing rules after enabling innovation

Despite substantial regulator engagement to enable early innovators in Kenya's digital credit market, policymakers failed to expeditiously formalize rules for the new sector, resulting in piecemeal supervision, ad hoc enforcement, and anti-competitive market concentration to the detriment of consumers. The extended delay between the launch of the new digital credit product with M-Shwari in 2012 and adoption of comprehensive regulation of the sector with the Central Bank of Kenya (Digital Credit Providers) Regulations in 2022 ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2022](#)) continues to haunt the Kenyan market today and poses valuable lessons for other markets.

The CBK was actually quite constructively engaged during the development of the CBA-Safaricom M-Shwari product, the 2012 launch of which our respondents broadly lauded as a positive market development (see Table 1 above). According to those involved in the process, when CBA and Safaricom conceived of M-Shwari there was extensive engagement between the M-Shwari team and CBK, including on policies around pricing, risk mitigation strategies, and loan provisioning. During the early days of M-Shwari there were also periodic meetings between CBK and CBA to review the loan portfolio.

This level of supervision for the first digital credit product demonstrates the type of oversight which could have been useful for monitoring digital credit overall as the market rapidly scaled and new lenders emerged from 2014. A policymaker active in digital credit policy since its inception provided a possible explanation for this lack of broader policy formalization over the first ten years of digital credit in Kenya:

“As a country we did not know where this was going to reach. When digital credit started, we did not think traditional moneylenders would move to the mobile loan apps. It's difficult for policy and regulation to chase innovation, but that is what we did not visualize. It has become a very big problem we are now grappling with, both in consumer protection and money laundering.”

In addition to delays in formalizing rules around bank-lenders of digital credit, efforts to oversee non-bank lenders were even slower, creating inconsistent protections across customers of different institutions. This inconsistency in part had to do with the fact that in Kenya financial sector oversight was mainly based on the type of institution and not the types of products being offered to consumers. In the case of digital credit this meant that a bank and a fintech could offer similar app-based products to the exact same consumer, and there would be significant variation in the levels of oversight and consumer protection depending on which app the consumer used. This entity-based over activity-based approach to regulating digital lending ([Borio et al, 2022](#)) at least partially reflected ambiguity in the mandates of different regulatory agencies, as noted by a former policymaker:

“I think [the policy process] was slow because it wasn't clear as to whose docket does that fall under. No one really wanted to get involved in it. There was a lack of clarity on how this should be regulated, and who should regulate. Then add to that general inertia about regulatory policy itself.”

Ambiguity in the regulatory mandate of this commercial innovation may have created challenges to developing a comprehensive digital credit policy framework. For example, until 2016 M-Shwari did not disclose the cost of its loans on their menu pre-origination, going against requirements in the CBK Prudential Guidelines on Transparency. Despite CBK being notified of this issue by researchers as early as

2014, it was CAK not CBK that took action to enforce transparency rules, using their mandate under the Competition Act. Greater collaboration by regulators in those early days of digital credit may have led to more effective and comprehensive consumer protection policy. Instead, attempts to implement new consumer protection authorities were met with opposition from existing financial sector regulators such as CBK and SASRA – the savings and credit cooperative – who actively opposed both the Financial Services Authority and the Financial Markets Conduct Authority bills, but to this day have still not established dedicated consumer protection departments within their own agencies.

Alongside issues of coordination and collaboration across regulatory authorities, the regulatory culture of “test and see” ([Tarazi, 2010](#); [Muthiora, 2015](#)) related to Kenya’s prior launch of mobile money still had strong inertia when it came to the innovation of digital credit. With mobile money, regulators provided ad-hoc approval for the M-PESA system via a letter of no objections and later formalized this innovation through policy measures such as the 2014 National Payment Systems Act Regulations ([National Council for Law Reporting with the Authority of the Attorney-General, 2011](#)).

The regulatory ambiguity during the interim between the closely monitored launch of M-Shwari in 2012 and the issuance of the Central Bank of Kenya (Digital Credit Providers) Regulations in 2022 ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2022](#)) resulted in increased consumer risks, lack of accountability, and an uneven playing field for different types of digital credit providers, including the following examples.

- **Inconsistent requirements regarding key consumer protection principles for bank and non-bank lenders.** The lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework led to inconsistent application of rules to bank and non-bank lenders. This included rules on pricing transparency and the ability of consumers to seek redress with financial sector authorities when they were abused by non-bank digital credit providers. Piecemeal activities sought to plug regulatory gaps, such as CAK’s 2016 pricing transparency order for mobile financial services that included mobile loans ([Business Daily Africa, 2016](#)). However, as captured in Table 1 above, the inconsistent application of rules by provider type were some of the clearest examples where respondents interviewed indicated they would have changed outcomes.
- **Exceptions to banking rules for bank-based digital credit loans.** An example from Kenya demonstrates how differential treatment of fees and charges can enable firms to avoid compliance with the spirit of pricing rules. In 2018 the Kenyan High Court found that because they referred to their charges as a “facilitation fee” not interest charges, M-Shwari loans were not covered by the interest rate caps placed on bank loans in 2016 ([Business Daily Africa, 2018](#)). This ruling led to other banks using similar terminology to avoid having to make their digital loans comply with the interest rate caps. Table 1 reveals that many of our respondents considered this a clear negative event in the history of the market.
- **Credit reporting requirements with incomplete reach and inadequate enforcement.** In 2014 the CRB regulations were amended to *allow* for non-bank lender participation. However, non-banks were not *compelled* to participate, such that positive information of borrowers from non-banks was mostly not entered into the CRBs. Even among some bank-based lenders, there was refusal to report positive digital loan records to the CRBs ([Mazer et al., 2016](#)) despite the requirement that banks report both positive and negative data for these loans. Still in 2023, several interviewees shared that compliance with credit reporting of digital loans by banks was not consistent or in full compliance. Interviewees suggested that one large lender, in particular, only reported digital loans once they were closed and mentioned analysis suggesting discrepancies

between lenders' reported digital loan portfolios and the number of records submitted to the CRBs indicative of underreporting of digital loans to the CRBs.

The delay in comprehensive regulation of digital credit was not for a lack of awareness of growing risks and harms. In fact, the Digital Lenders Association of Kenya (DLAK), the industry body representing the larger non-bank lenders, was asking for regulations by 2019 ([Ambadala, 2019](#)). And, conduct and competition concerns were raised early by local researchers, industry actors, and policymakers. Some policymakers did take individual actions within their mandate where possible in areas such as consumer protection. And, the National Treasury put forth two separate bills to address market conduct and coverage gaps for consumer lenders (the Financial Services Authority Bill, 2016, and the Financial Market Conduct Authority Bill, 2018), which were both tabled after significant pushback from financial sector regulators ([Kenyan Wall Street, 2018](#)). In the end, the necessary policy reforms in digital credit lagged innovation by up to a decade, creating issues of consumer protection, credit reporting, effective supervision, and competition that are the topics of discussion in Reflections #2-4 below.

Even with some key reforms now in place, interviewees expressed concerns about Kenya's current policy position. As one policymaker noted, "There is a big gap around credit not being regulated as an activity. It is by sector. It has taken a long time for there to be an articulation of the Central Bank on regulating digital lenders, and this still won't cover the whole credit piece." Another policy expert cautioned that even as the past decade of innovations are addressed in recent policy reforms, Kenya may still not be anticipating the next challenges, "Digital credit has now moved to different things, crypto and blockchain, packaging of credit with other products. Regulation has just caught up to digital credit and now it is moving onto something else." Whether the next wave of digital credit innovations such as blockchain, embedded finance, or buy now pay later products will receive proper and prompt policy oversight remains to be seen. But, from the first ten years of digital credit in Kenya it is clear that the policy response to the first wave of digital lending was late and insufficient. Other markets would do well to learn the lesson to formalize and expand rules early in the cycle of digital credit market expansion.

Reflection #2: Consumer protection matters and needs to be addressed early on

Digital credit can be a benefit for many, but, like all high-cost consumer lending, it raises significant consumer protection risks for some. The Kenya experience demonstrates that the high cost of digital credit, the ease of access, and the lack of consumer protection rules and oversight contribute to several key risks for consumers.

Lack of pricing transparency. When digital credit emerged in Kenya, some lenders did not even disclose the cost of the loan to consumers on the mobile screen before they accepted their loan. Others had ethically questionable terms in their service agreements, including improper use of data ([Ombija et al., 2016](#)).³ Over time, transparency of terms did improve in part through policy reforms and provider improvements to their interfaces ([Mazer, 2018](#); [Mazer et al., 2017](#)). But, some of the issues such as unfair contract terms remained an issue and consumers continue to cite challenges with unexpected fees and charges in mobile loans, including 32% of borrowers in the 2021 FinAccess Survey ([FDS Kenya, 2021](#)).

³ It is worth noting that this example was published in 2016, but it took several more years before the issue of social shaming and use of contacts was addressed by policymakers or industry, and even today reports of this practice continue. See [Kiriori \(2023\)](#).

Cost of digital loans. How to determine whether digital loans are “suitable,” in regulatory terms, or, more colloquially, “too expensive” remains a topic of debate among researchers, but broadly depends on factors such as the return on the use of the loan, the ability for consumers to effectively assess the true cost of the loan, income to interest ratios, and the costs of alternative options to obtain funds ([Garz et al., 2021](#)). Although stakeholders interviewed had mixed feelings on whether digital credit in Kenya was too expensive, there are clear aspects of digital credit pricing that raise concerns beyond the overall cost.⁴

First, there are the high penalty rates applied for non-repayment. Market pioneer M-Shwari still charges a penalty rate for not repaying the loan in 30 days of 7.5% ([Safaricom, n.d.b.](#)), which is equal to the regular interest rate CBA charges for most M-Shwari loans. In other words, missing the repayment date results in at least a doubling of regular interest charges.⁵ This practice is common in digital credit in Kenya, and can lead to high penalty fees for non-repayment.

Second, there is an apparent lack of what many practitioners refer to as “risk-based pricing” that one would expect in markets where lenders have to compete on loan pricing. Specifically, those who repay loans on time do not receive discounted interest rates on subsequent loans. As CAK’s Digital Credit Market Inquiry reports, many borrowers not only pay on time, they pay early: “37.5% of accounts have an average effective tenure of less than four weeks, and 5.1% have an average effective tenure of one week or less,” with 4% repaying their loan in less than one day ([Putman et al., 2021](#)). However, in many cases these consumers were not given discounts on their fees for early repayment, nor did they see their cost of loan reduce on their subsequent loans. For these reasons, CAK recommended “refunding a portion of finance charges for the many borrowers who repay digital loans well before their due date; and reducing the proportion of fees to loan value charged to repeat borrowers who consistently repaid prior loans ([Putman et al., 2021](#)).”

Debt stress and loan defaults. As illustrated in Figure 2, the FSDK FinAccess household survey has documented continuous declines in Kenyan’s financial health across the 2016, 2019, and 2021 survey rounds.⁶ While much of the 2021 decline can be explained by the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the economy, there are some signs that digital credit may be part of the story of deteriorating financial health in Kenya ([Gubbins et al., 2022](#)). By 2019, 30% of the population had “low” financial health up from 15% in 2016. This number grew to 39% in 2021. By 2019, 69.9% of the adult population already reported borrowing, which was up from 58.4% in 2013 with the increase largely driven by digital credit. The 2021 survey only saw an increase of 4.1 percentage points to 74.0% of adults. Additionally, by 2019, 18.0% and 9.4% of mobile loan users already reported having defaulted on a mobile bank loan and app loan, respectively ([FSD Kenya, 2020](#)), though these numbers did increase substantially to 50.9% and 46.3% in

⁴ It is worth noting that a recent court ruling has extended the “*in duplum*” rule to all lenders in Kenya, so no digital loans will have total charges exceeding the loan amount going forward. See [Bowmans \(2022\)](#).

⁵ While M-Shwari calls these charges a “facilitation fee,” they are by nature equivalent to interest charges common on loan products, and so the authors refers to this charge as “interest” not “facilitation fee.”

⁶ Financial health can be understood as the extent to which a person or family can smoothly manage their current financial obligations and have confidence in their financial future and is typically conceived as being made up of three elements: smoothly managing short-term financial obligations and consumption needs, being capable of absorbing financial shocks and staying on track to reach long term goals. A fourth, more subjective element, is often included in the definition and involves feeling confident and in control of one’s finances. Drawing on the predominant definitions of financial health, FSD Kenya developed the multi-dimensional financial health index- an experimental measure to gauge the financial health of adults using the nationally representative FinAccess survey.

2021. A consumer survey conducted as part of CAK’s Digital Credit Market Inquiry further confirmed the high incidence of digital loan default with 77% of borrowers having been late repaying a loan at some point. The Inquiry also found that 33% of borrowers had multiple mobile loans at some point prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, which increased to 44% thereafter ([Putman et al., 2021](#)).

Figure 2. FinAccess household survey results on level of financial health: 2016, 2019, 2021

Debt collection practices. In Kenya, consumers have raised unethical and even illegal debt collection practices from digital lenders. This includes aggressive collection practices, and even “social shaming,” wherein guarantors or individuals listed in the borrower’s phone are contacted to shame the borrower into repaying their loan ([Kiriori, 2023](#)). One consumer consulted for this project was one day late repaying a digital loan and immediately began receiving threatening calls and SMS (see Figure 3), as well as calls from the lender to their parents, sister, and brother, threatening consequences if the borrower did not repay the loan. This practice was employed by many digital credit providers in Kenya ([Kiruga, 2020](#)). To address these practices, the Digital Credit Provider Regulations prohibit the use of such tactics as part of lenders’ debt collection practices, explicitly prohibiting access to borrowers’ contact lists, posting their information online for purposes of shaming, and unauthorized or unsolicited calls or messages to the customer’s contacts ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2022](#)). While these collection practices have declined, they still continue in some cases, as evidenced by recent media articles and consumer outcry such as a petition seeking the removal of one such digital lender from the market for social shaming ([Kihiu, 2022](#)). As one Kenyan fintech founder noted:

“One of the big concerns was the debt collection practices. We saw once big actors proved the model was possible a lot of actors came in and used debt collection practices which broke the trust of digital lenders with the government and the customer base.”

Due to your REFUSAL to cooperate and pay your loan, we are under STRICT instructions to start dispatching harsh messages and numerous interval disturbing calls to your CONTACT Referees(extended family,friends and colleagues) including sending screenshot of how you USED them as Referees to acquire

Figure 3. Threatening message sent by a digital lender to a borrower who was late repaying their loan.

Fraudulent lending offers and providers. In addition to misconduct from genuine digital lenders, the digital credit boom in Kenya was accompanied by the rise of fraudulent behavior ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2018](#)). This fraud primarily consisted of two types: 1. Fake loan offers sent via SMS or phone call, and 2. Fraudulent loan apps on the Google Play Store. These scams frequently sought to obtain consumers' sensitive personal and financial information to then be used to commit fraud against the consumer. In other cases, the fraudster sought to convince the consumer to sign up for the product and pay upfront fees for things like "registration" or "loan application review," while not actually offering any loan to the consumer. A 2019 audit of loan apps by FSDK found that more than 100 mobile apps on the two main app stores with many of these apps either charging very high registration fees relative to loans disbursed or failing to actually make loans whatsoever ([Gwer et al, 2019](#)). These challenges are hardly limited to Kenya with Fu and Mishra ([2022](#)) documenting the ubiquity of predatory or outright fraudulent apps on leading app stores and hundreds of millions of predatory app downloads around the world.

These negative aspects of digital credit have impacted millions of borrowers over the first decade of digital credit in Kenya. In the face of these issues, a range of policy responses were taken, with the most noteworthy being the issuing of the Digital Credit Provider Regulations in 2022. Table 2 below presents some of the noteworthy consumer protection actions taken, and an analysis of their impact and consequences.

As Table 2 shows, many of the early policy activities did not result in legally enforceable consumer protection provisions, especially for non-bank digital lenders. It is also noteworthy how those policies that were put in place were relatively narrow in focus, covering a specific topic such as pricing transparency, or interest rates. There were attempts to address consumer protection and conduct issues using a holistic approach, such as the recommendations from the CAK's "Competition and consumer protection in the Kenyan banking sector" market inquiry report ([Competition Authority of Kenya, 2017](#)), and the proposed 2018 Financial Market Conduct Authority Bill ([The National Treasury of Kenya, 2018](#)). However, these efforts did not yield tangible policy reforms to address consumer protection concerns.

Despite growing recognition of consumer protection issues, financial sector authorities demonstrated limited response and even opposition to broader policy reforms which would have established new mandates and authorities to address these abusive practices in the industry. Even as the Digital Credit

Provider Regulations have put in place consumer protection standards for all digital lenders, the implementation of this regulation and its enforcement is not being handled by a new dedicated digital credit or fintech unit, nor a consumer protection unit, but has been added to the tasks of the Banking Supervision Department within CBK, whose principal policy priority is prudential supervision. That the Central Bank of Kenya still does not count with a dedicated consumer protection department, makes Kenya an outlier globally for a market of this maturity and state of innovation. Globally, 75 percent of countries have a separate unit or team designated to work on consumer protection; for lower middle income countries, it is 76 percent ([World Bank, 2017](#)). This raises questions regarding the policy resources available to execute the new consumer protection in digital credit mandate, which is discussed in Reflection #4.

Reflecting on the consumer protection concerns that quickly arose with digital credit in Kenya, a long-time participant in the industry summed up the dilemma Kenya faced as such:

“I find this so interesting, and I think other countries can learn from it. There is no honeymoon period. One day you have no credit access, and the next day you have very bad actors. I’m not surprised it took the policymakers a while to wake up because everything happened so fast. And this idea that these were startups, and they had good experiences with M-PESA and M-Shwari in the past, the bias to think this would all work out well was quite high.”

One of the risks of the “Test and Learn” regulatory culture mentioned in Reflection #1 is that it can leave consumer protection unaddressed. In comparison, the alternative approaches to more formally and cautiously piloting financial innovation, such as regulatory sandboxes or innovation hubs, often include consumer protection rules as standard, though each approach has its own shortcomings.⁷

The warning signs on consumer protection in Kenya began flashing early on and were supported again and again through research findings. But, a lack of consumer protection policy reforms and limited investment in consumer protection supervision meant these issues went under-addressed, and consumers suffered unnecessary abusive practices. For digital and similar innovations, policymakers in other markets can learn from the lesson of Kenya to prioritize consumer protection policy in digital credit from its inception and remain open to the needed updates to the policy architecture to sustainably deliver on consumer protection as the market evolves.

⁷ Regulatory sandboxes and innovation hubs allow new providers with innovative ideas the ability to test these ideas in the market for a limited time and limited scale without having to comply with all the regulatory requirements typical for that product type. They are intended to create low-burden spaces to safely test new products and services while still adhering to key policy goals like consumer protection and financial soundness.

Table 2. Consumer protection relevant digital credit policy developments in Kenya

Year	Milestone	Enforceable provisions?	Impact on digital credit
2013	CBK issues Consumer Protection Guidelines for entities under their supervision (Cost of Credit, 2013)	Yes	Provisions would apply to bank-based lenders, so could impact their digital products. However, it is worth noting that early bank lenders were not disclosing costs of mobile loans until the CAK order in 2016.
2016	CAK issues price transparency rules (Mazer, 2016)	Yes	Improved price transparency across all digital lender types
2016	Financial Services Authority Bill published by Treasury (The National Treasury of Kenya, 2016)	No	None. Bill was tabled after opposition from financial sector regulators.
2016	Bank interest rate cap law (Central Bank of Kenya, 2016)	Yes	None. Not enforced for digital credit.
2017	CAK issues “Competition and consumer protection in the Kenyan banking sector” report (Competition Authority of Kenya, 2017)	No	Unclear. No direct policy reforms out of inquiry.
2018	Court rules M-Shwari loans don’t have to comply with interest rate cap (Guguyu, 2018)	Yes	Prevented bank digital lenders from having to comply with interest rate cap.
2018	Draft Financial Market Conduct Authority Bill published by Treasury (The National Treasury of Kenya, 2018)	No	None. Bill was tabled after opposition from CBK and others.

2018	Public notice regarding fraudulent financial services, products and applications (Central Bank of Kenya, 2018)	No	Unclear. Did not require any changes from providers.
2019	Google issues rules for app store loans, including 60-day minimum loan term (Amadala, 2019)	No	Unclear. Provisions appear to have not been enforced as 30-day loans remained common in Play Store.
2019	Data Protection Act signed into law (Office of the Data Protection Commissioner in Kenya, 2019)	Yes	Codified data privacy rules, established additional authority to take action on data privacy violations of digital lenders.
2019	DLAK issues member code of conduct (Mbego, 2019)	No	Set standards for member conduct, although not enforceable legally.
2021	CAK publishes Digital Credit Market Inquiry report (Putman et al, 2021)	No	Unclear. No direct policy reforms out of inquiry.
2022	CBK issues Digital Credit Provider Regulations (Central Bank of Kenya, 2022)	Yes	Established oversight of non-bank lenders and consumer protection obligations.
2022	Google issues new rules for Play Store, pledges to remove non-licensed lenders (CM Advocates LLP, 2023)	Yes	Evidence of removal of some lenders from App Store for non-compliance with new rules.

Reflection #3: Credit reference bureaus and data sharing rules must keep pace with digital innovation

In Kenya, digital credit created new challenges for a credit information system that was only a few years old when M-Shwari launched. The speed of digital credit underwriting and short loan term meant that digital credit was not suited to the monthly updating of credit information from banks. Digital credit also expanded the credit bureau from what one local expert estimated was only 700,000 borrowers at the launch of digital credit, to more than 18 million borrowers in the bureaus today. This growth created new challenges for data submission, data quality monitoring, and use of millions of small loan records to inform credit-making decisions.

The CRB regulations also created an uneven playing field for digital lenders and diminished the potential value of CRB data. The regulations did not require non-banks to submit information to the credit bureaus and allowed those that did submit to only submit negative information, such as reports on late payment, default, etc. Positive information, such as reports of early or on-time interest payments, loan repayment, etc., was often excluded from submissions such that most borrowers who repaid their digital loans to non-banks did not get credit for this positive behavior in the CRB system ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2013](#); [Central Bank of Kenya, 2020](#)). In 2020, non-banks lenders were outright prohibited from participating in the credit bureau ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2020](#)). Only those non-bank lenders who have received a digital credit provider license will be able to participate in the credit information system going forward.

Another challenge to CRB coverage was bank-based digital lenders initial refusal to submit positive records to the credit bureaus, with CBA not reporting positive records until 2016 ([Mazer et al., 2016](#)). Similarly, Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya (CIS-K) analysis in 2017 found large data gaps and uneven reporting by lenders across the three CRBs (Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya, 2017). Multiple respondents from the industry confirmed that some of the larger bank-based digital lenders continue to avoid reporting active digital loans to the bureaus and reported that analysis has revealed substantial differences in number of mobile loans reported in annual reports and financial statements versus number of loans reported to the credit bureaus by some bank-based digital lenders. This indicates that compliance and enforcement may still be an issue for credit reporting of digital loans. One of the Kenyan policy experts interviewed explained:

“Compliance is still not great. I can only speak to the bank [digital] lenders. Because there has been suppression of digital...there are instances where you look at a [loan] portfolio, and look at the number of submissions in the bureau, and you see a disparity. The CRBs will say it seems like they are not submitting data, and they take an old file and submit that to the bureau.”

Non-compliance with reporting of positive loan records, as well as lax lending policies of some digital credit providers, led to a disproportionately large number of negative digital loan records appearing in the CRBs. In March, 2017 MicroSave Consulting documented more than 2.7 million negative listings for mobile loans in the credit bureaus ([Mustafa et al, 2017](#)). Lack of full-file reporting to credit bureaus by digital lenders and non-compliance with full-file reporting obligations of banks has led to a disproportionate number of negative listings in the credit information system.

The 2020 updates to the CRB regulations helped to address this issue by establishing a minimum threshold of Ksh1,000 for reporting of negative loan information, prohibiting the sharing of negative information from April 1, 2021 to September 30, 2021, and requiring CRBs to provide first-time clearance certificates free of charge ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2020](#)). As a result, in 2020 more than 4 million negative records in the CRBs were delisted ([Mukere, 2022](#)).

In part to address the issue of negative digital loan records in the CRBs, additional reforms were made in 2021 and 2022 to the CRBs. In November, 2021 the CBK ordered:

“Loans below Ksh.5 million that fall in arrears from October 1, 2021 to September 30, 2022, will not lead to the ‘blacklisting’ of the borrower on the Credit Reference Bureaus (CRBs). Further, CRBs will not include in any credit report, any negative credit information for loans of a customer less than Ksh.5 million submitted to the CRB from October 1, 2020 to September 30, 2021, for a period of 12 months from October 1, 2021 to September 30, 2022 ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2021](#)).”

In October, 2022, the CBK issued the “Credit Repair Framework,” which focused on non-performing mobile loans, and required digital lenders to:

“provide a discount of at least fifty percent of the non-performing mobile phone digital loans outstanding as at end October 2022, and update the borrowers credit standing from non-performing to performing. The institution will then enter into a repayment plan with the borrowers for a period up to May 31, 2023, for the balance of the loan. Upon expiry of the Framework, the credit standing of the borrowers with respect to these loans will depend on their repayment performance during the six-month period ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2022](#)).”

The CBK estimated this policy could impact more than 4.2 million borrowers with a total outstanding loan value of around US\$210 million. It is not clear yet to what extent borrowers have taken up this opportunity to repair their credit history through partial repayment, but it will be worth monitoring the final outcome to see how effective this approach can be as a way to address the high number of small-value negative listings in the CRBs.

In summarizing the experience of digital credit and the Kenyan credit information system, there are three specific themes from which other markets can learn: market coverage, compliance and enforcement, and adaptability of CRBs to digital financial services.

Market coverage. Kenya’s CRB framework was not updated in a timely manner to cover all the various types of digital lenders that emerged. Even as third-party credit providers were permitted to submit data to CRBs in 2014, they were not compelled. They were also allowed to submit negative listings only if they chose. Bank-based digital lenders were required to submit full-file information to the bureaus, creating an uneven playing field for digital lenders regarding reporting to the credit bureaus. Given the proliferation of negative listings which arose in the CRBs in subsequent years, requiring participating third-parties to report full-file information from the onset may have been preferable.

Compliance and enforcement. Lack of requirement of full-file reporting for non-banks, and non-compliance in reporting positive loans by banks, meant that the impact of digital credit on CRBs was disproportionately negative as compared to the reality of repayment behavior in the market. The majority of loans in digital credit are repaid, so if lenders were required to report both positive and negative information, you would have seen more positive records. Market leader M-Shwari refused to report

positive records to the CRBs, despite reporting repayment rates of approximately 98%, only agreeing to comply with this requirement in 2016. This means that millions of good paying customers were denied the ability to leverage their positive credit history for several years. As noted above, there are reports that non-compliance continues today for some bank-based digital lenders, and there appears to be a view of some in the industry that the rules of credit reporting do not apply to their digital credit customers as they do to other customers of theirs.

Enforcing compliance could be complicated by the supervisory structure of Kenya's Credit Information System. Third-party credit providers, which include non-bank digital lenders, have been placed under the supervision of CIS-K, an organization established by industry and CBK to support the implementation of an effective credit information sharing mechanism. These third-party providers must comply with the CIS-K Code of Conduct to participate in the credit information system (Mazer, 2018b). However banks' participation is governed by different rules, and they are directly supervised by CBK. As digital credit providers become licensed by CBK, supervision of these lenders will also transfer from CIS-K to CBK. This bifurcated mode of supervision could prove challenging to coordinate, and places additional burden on CBK's Banking Supervision Department to monitor compliance in an area which may be more suited to CIS-K's core functions.

Adaptability of CRBs to digital financial services. If policymakers are serious about making credit information sharing work for digital lending in Kenya, they need to move beyond the 30 days reporting window, ideally to real-time reporting or, failing that, daily batching. The credit reporting framework in Kenya does not currently match the digital-based credit system which dominates the Kenyan market. It was only in 2019 that the first credit reporting template for digital loans was issued ([Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya, 2019](#)) and the 2020 CRB Regulations still allow for submission of data on a monthly basis. Interviews with numerous digital lenders reveal how only requiring monthly reporting has made the CRB data less useful for digital lending, as it does not provide a timely view of a consumer's borrowing behavior when many digital loans are short-term, often repaid in less than 30 days, and consumers can easily borrow multiple new loans in a single day. Real time reporting or at least daily batching is certainly technically feasible. Someone with knowledge of current reporting practices confirmed that one of the larger digital lenders is already doing hourly updating of their data in the credit information system. The benefits of real-time sharing could be substantial. One lender who was able to integrate into the Safaricom API and have loan applicants consent to share their M-PESA statements with the lender during the application process reported being able to see that more than half of applicants had taken loans with other digital lenders, something that would not be possible using the monthly credit bureau data.

It is unclear why Kenya's credit information system has not been updated to match the needs of Kenya's predominantly digital formal credit ecosystem. It is clear though that the lack of reforms reduces the utility of the credit information system for digital lenders, has led to disproportionate volumes of negative loan records, and has reduced the ability of firms to properly rate credit risk and consumers to benefit from their credit history. There is no shortage of new credit information systems and even more complex data sharing systems, such as open finance, proliferating across the globe ([Mazer, 2023](#)). For policymakers overseeing rapidly growing digital credit markets, they should look to those models for solutions that will ensure credit information flows nearly as fast as the digital credit products themselves.

Reflection #4: Robust investment in policy architecture and supervisory staffing is needed for proper market monitoring

The Kenyan example demonstrates how delays in digital credit regulations and insufficient investment in supervisory capacity can constrain private sector innovation and distort entry consistent with competitive markets even once proper regulation is in place.

Since the Digital Credit Provider Regulations were issued by CBK in March 2022, under-resourced supervisors have struggled to keep pace with the demand for provider licenses. The 2022 regulations require those providing digital credit to be licensed as a Digital Credit Provider (DCP) and applicants began to apply for licenses nearly immediately. Over the first six months after the regulation's issuance, a reported 288 applications for a DCP license were submitted, with the first 10 licenses being issued in September 2022 ([Nderi, 2022](#)). Since then two additional rounds of license approvals have been announced, with a total of 32 approved licenses and 401 license applications as of March 2023 ([Central Bank of Kenya, 2023](#)).

Over a year since the opening of the window for licenses, there remain hundreds of pending digital credit provider applications. This creates both business and regulatory uncertainty for digital lenders. On the business side, there is evidence that delays in licensing have hampered the ability of lenders to secure crucial funding—which is sometimes unlocked once a DCP license is granted ([Muiruri, 2023](#)). On the regulatory side, lack of a license has left many providers in a state of limbo. In late 2022, Google announced that it would remove all non-licensed DCPs from its Play Store in 2023, and in March it did remove several hundred apps ([Njanja, 2023](#)). Google has said the lenders who are awaiting a decision on their DCP license can present the pending application to avoid removal; however, this still leaves most DCPs in a relatively precarious position if Google changes this policy at any point before CBK has completed review of their application.

Lenders consulted for this interview reported that smaller lenders were struggling in the interim, and some have even reached out to larger lenders wondering if they can leverage their license to continue operations. One digital lender told *Business Daily Africa* in January 2023, “The truth is that we are worried it’s taking too long. We believe that the CBK may be suffering from capacity issues and is overwhelmed by the number of applications ([Muiruri, 2023](#)).”

Despite the substantial time and resources DCP licensing and eventual supervision will require, the licensing process is being handled by the Banking Supervision Department in CBK, which is already responsible for prudential supervision of banks and deposit-taking microfinance banks, consumer protection supervision, CRBs, and foreign exchange. One digital credit provider commented:

“It is creating issues that this licensing process is so slow, and it’s curious that licensing is being handled not by a new team, but by banking supervision, who also has to do things like bank mergers.”

Kenya finally formalized non-bank digital lenders, which primarily require market conduct and consumer protection oversight. Yet, the country still lacks both a dedicated department focused on non-bank digital lenders and a dedicated consumer protection department.

This experience with licensing of DCPs in Kenya suggests two lessons for other markets. First, the longer a delay in formalizing oversight of a sector such as non-bank digital credit, the more of a backlog of work

and possibly delays and uncertainty could arise. Second, there is a need to invest in the supervisory infrastructure and resources needed to effectively implement regulation, licensing, and ongoing oversight.

Reflection #5: Digital credit requires robust pro-competition policy

As described in the market overview section above, Kenya’s digital credit market is both crowded and concentrated. Digital credit relies on low-cost, easily accessible electronic payments, which places payment service providers, such as mobile money operators (MMOs), in a central position in the digital credit value chain. In Kenya, Safaricom dominates the payments market, holding 97% of mobile money accounts at the end of 2022 ([Communications Authority of Kenya, 2022](#)). This dominance is leveraged to advantage Safaricom’s digital credit partners in several ways:

- 1. Promotion and placement of products on the M-PESA menu.** The M-Shwari, KCB M-PESA, and Fuliza loan products are the only loans which are listed on the M-PESA menu. The ubiquity of M-PESA in the lives of Kenyans means that placement on the menu and promotional SMS which are sent out by Safaricom to M-PESA customers reaches 97% of the mobile money customer base, giving these loans advantages in visibility, access, and targeted marketing. In addition, the disbursements and collection of these loans does not incur fees where other lenders have to pay bulk payment fees.
- 2. Access to data for credit scoring and targeting.** Safaricom provided useful data on M-PESA transactions, airtime usage, and other key indicators to help NCBA and KCB build their credit decisioning models. The M-PESA transaction data, in particular, offers valuable cash-flow information that other lenders have struggled to obtain through workarounds, such as scraping the contents of loan applicants’ SMS messages. As noted above, one lender who had access to borrowers’ M-PESA statements via an API found it highly valuable to identify risky behaviors such as gambling or multiple borrowing. Similarly, Mazer (2018) documents the experience of a digital lender who had access to the short-lived Safaricom credit score being promoted among some fintechs at the time. This lender found the Safaricom data substantially outperformed their existing set of data ([Mazer, 2018b](#)), demonstrating the power of verifiable cash-flow, identity, and other information contained within M-PESA accounts.
- 3. Sweeping of funds.** As Fuliza’s terms and conditions note, “Safaricom shall automatically debit the amounts due from the credits deposited or received into your M-PESA Account at any time until the Facility is cleared in full ([Safaricom, n.d.c](#)).” The ability to sweep loan repayments instead of waiting on a customer to push repayment is a significant advantage in managing debt collection. This is even more valuable when the account being swept is as essential as M-PESA is to many Kenyans’ lives and, therefore, less likely to be abandoned to avoid loan repayment.
- 4. SIM toolkit access.** Most digital lenders have to rely on apps to offer their products, while many banks have built their own USSD shortcodes. By contrast, NCBA and KCB can be accessed via the SIM Toolkit of Safaricom. This can improve the reliability and reduce the cost of operating the channel, as well as make it easier to serve consumers who do not have smartphones or who reside in areas with poor data connectivity. Analysis of bank USSD transactions by Stax in 2022 found that, “In a sample of 33,743 Stax USSD transactions performed in Kenya in 2022, more than 50%

failed due to a network error ([Shorland, 2023](#)).” The consequences of this preferential access is most relevant for lower-income and rural Kenyans, who are less likely to be able to use over-the-top solutions, such as lending apps, and who are, therefore, only able to access digital credit via the Safaricom menu. In this way, millions of Kenyans are limited in practical terms to the handful of Safaricom-supported choices in digital credit, despite there being hundreds of digital lenders active in Kenya.⁸

The M-PESA mobile money and digital credit monopoly, with market shares of 97% and 95%, respectively, has a level of dominance in Kenya that is almost without precedent for a non state-owned financial enterprise. Pointing out the monopoly-level dominance of M-PESA is not to disparage the success and innovation of Safaricom and its partners; it is merely a reflection of the facts of the market in Kenya. And, these facts have real consequences for consumers. As the CAK Digital Credit Market Inquiry noted, consumers do not receive as much of a discount on their loans as you would expect after proving themselves through on-time repayment. Further, lower-income and rural consumers are more at risk of being locked into the options presented on the M-PESA menu. Finally, consumer choice and switching is severely restricted as consumers cannot freely share their personal data with other lenders or rely on the dominant bank digital lenders to fully comply in reporting their full credit histories to the CRBs. For policymakers to effectively enable pro-consumer competition and innovation in the digital credit sector, these issues of menu and channel access, data usage, and sweeping of funds should not be overlooked.

More generally, the trajectory of Kenya’s digital credit market reveals how vertical integration and lack of competition enabling policies can lead to market consolidation. For this reason, competition policy needs to be an early aspect of digital credit policy frameworks, alongside robust consumer protection supervision and modernized credit and data-sharing infrastructure.

Discussion: What can other markets learn from Kenya’s decade of digital credit?

Financial regulation and supervision should balance the benefits of innovation with the risks of consumer harms and costs of unequal competition. Taking a disciplined look at the evidence on the impacts of digital credit on economic growth and household consumption smoothing suggests limited benefits from the first generation of digital credit. The evidence underwhelms even when just comparing the outcomes of digital credit to the more limited expectations and aspirations of the sector’s practitioners to empower microentrepreneurs. Commercial marketing and social impact sector rhetoric notwithstanding, it is perhaps not fair to put the expectation of enterprise development, robust growth, and transformative development impacts on the shoulders of small-value digital credit. However, it is fair to say that, if the impacts of digital credit growth are modest, then the downside consequences become more relevant.

During interviews with Kenyan digital credit stakeholders, they were asked to recall what the initial expectations were for digital credit in Kenya. Most respondents included access to credit for small and micro enterprises as one of the expectations. While separating personal and commercial uses of digital credit can be difficult to disentangle among the low-income population segment that must often rely on

⁸ For a comprehensive review of USSD and competition in mobile financial services, see [Competition Authority of Kenya \(2016\)](#), which led to price caps on wholesale USSD charges for digital financial services, including digital credit.

informal entrepreneurship financed from personal household balance sheets, surveys of digital credit users consistently report household and consumption spending as the primary uses of these loans. This should not be surprising as the relatively small value of most digital credit loans limit their potential to support enterprise growth.

A recent review of the growing body of rigorous impact evaluations of digital credit products in Kenya and other markets highlights that the evidence fails to find consistently positive let alone transformative average impacts of digital credit on income or consumption smoothing. In addition to the hypothesized income generating impacts, which are not supported by the evidence, the potential for improved consumption smoothing would be compelling for low-income households, in particular, that are often prone to food insecurity in times of shocks. Unfortunately, the select findings of consumption smoothing are not robust across evaluations. [Robinson et al. \(2022\)](#) finds “Overall, there is little evidence that access to credit has consistent positive impacts on borrower welfare, though two impact evaluations document positive effects on resilience [consumption smoothing] and subjective well-being, respectively. No study finds statistically significant negative impacts of digital credit.”⁹

As noted in this report, there were substantial conduct and competition issues which arose in the first ten years of digital credit in Kenya. These issues remained under-addressed for a decade due to a lack of appropriate policy reforms and inadequate supervision and enforcement. In markets where digital credit is emerging, policymakers can learn from the following lessons of Kenya’s experience to effectively mitigating the downside risks of digital credit while simultaneously supporting market expansion:

1. **Allow new innovations to emerge in pilot stages and then monitor them closely as was done with M-Shwari in Kenya, but with two modifications:** a) Once innovations have proven their viability, formalize rules and policies to ensure a level playing field early on; b). Consider more formal and transparent tools like regulatory sandboxes rather than ad-hoc individual approval of new products and innovations to ensure fair evaluation of pilots and to embed consumer protection rules into each pilot. The unregulated digital lending sector was left unsupervised until 2022. In the interim, significant conduct issues arose and Kenyan consumers suffered because of unequal protection for bank and non-bank digital loans.
2. **Set market conduct and consumer protection rules early, and enforce them diligently.** Digital credit and other innovative models may require new consumer protection rules, new consumer protection supervisory methods, or even new consumer protection authorities. Policymakers in other markets should act early to enshrine consumer protection rights and requirements in digital credit, and support establishing new departments or authorities if necessary.
3. **Modernize credit bureaus to keep pace with the digital age.** Key design weaknesses reduced the usefulness of credit bureaus to digital lenders and undermined the value digital lenders could have contributed to the bureaus. The 30-day batch reporting requirements remain out of date and inconsistent with the near real-time pace underwriting pace of current business models. There are many examples of real-time data sharing solutions which could solve this issue. Additionally, with the exception of the small portion who have received their digital credit provider licenses, most non-bank digital lenders remain prohibited from participating in the CRBs since they were removed in 2020. This limited coverage advantages the incumbents and undermines the representativeness of CRB data. Policymakers in other markets should not let the

⁹ See also [Mazer \(2021\)](#).

CRB policy architecture become outdated as credit markets become faster, more diverse, and digital.

4. **Invest in supervisory capacity and organizational structures.** Implementing all the policy reforms suggested above requires new and different resources from traditional activities, such as prudential supervision. Without such investment, issues like the long delays in digital provider licensing approvals in Kenya can occur. In Kenya the financial sector policy architecture is still underdeveloped, lacking both i) a dedicated unit focused on digital credit and fintechs, and ii) a consumer protection department within CBK or standalone consumer protection authority. There are examples from across Africa and beyond of how central banks have updated their organizational infrastructure to build robust consumer protection and fintech or financial innovation units. Markets where digital credit is emerging should begin these conversations early, so that the capacity and infrastructure is in place when digital credit or other fintech innovations scale to the level they have in Kenya.
5. **Protect against anti-competitive risks common to digital models.** The level of market concentration in mobile money in Kenya is particularly high. But, it is not uncommon to find MMOs with over 50% market share across African economies. Dominance in payments and control over key infrastructure like USSD and SMS can allow MMOs and their lending partners to gain competitive advantages in the digital credit market. Combined with lack of robust data-sharing rules and enforcement, there is the risk of a bifurcated digital credit market emerging like in Kenya. Where channel providers are partnering directly with digital credit providers, policymakers should seek to implement pro-competition policies which reduce the risk that market concentration in digital credit will approach the levels seen in Kenya.

With an eye to the future, respondents communicated a sense that Kenya is reaching a digital credit inflection point. There are an increasing number of providers seeking to use digital lending and repayment rails to offer more than just small-value consumer loans, targeting sectors such as agricultural finance, fast-moving consumer goods distribution chains, e-commerce, and other aspects of what is often referred to as “embedded finance.” Conversations with the firms developing these innovations show the potential that the digital credit model could have for real economic growth as reduced costs, faster underwriting, and better information on potential borrowers may lead to better credit risk assessments and more suitable products. The recommendations in this report focus primarily on what policymakers can learn from how Kenya handled the first ten years of a primarily consumer-driven digital credit boom. However, addressing these policy issues now could have the added benefit of facilitating the movement of digital credit into more productive parts of the economy, which remain credit constrained and for which the first generation of digital credit products were ill-matched.

References

- Amadala, V. (2019, August 23). *New Google app rules to deny borrowers quick mobile loans*. The Star. <https://www.the-star.co.ke/business/kenya/2019-08-23-new-google-app-rules-to-deny-borrowers-quick-mobile-loans/>
- Amadala, V. (2019, July 13). We are open to regulation, digital lenders tell CBK. The Star. <https://www.the-star.co.ke/business/kenya/2019-07-13-we-are-open-to-regulation-digital-lenders-tell-cbk/>
- Avgouleas, E., & Donald, D. (Eds.). (2019). *The Political Economy of Financial Regulation* (International Corporate Law and Financial Market Regulation). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/9781108612821.
- Babatunde, G. (2020, November 16). *Safaricom, Banks in Kenya Push to End Free Mobile Money Transfers Following Huge Revenue Loss*. Technext. <https://technext24.com/2020/11/16/safaricom-banks-in-kenya-push-to-end-free-mobile-money-transfers-following-huge-revenue-loss/>
- Blackmon, W., Mazer, R., & Warren, S. (2021, March). *Kenya Consumer Protection in Digital Finance Survey*. Innovations for Poverty Action and Competition Authority of Kenya. <https://poverty-action.org/sites/default/files/Kenya-Consumer-Survey-Report.pdf>
- Bock, P. (2016, May 5). *This startup gives credit ratings based on personality*. Wired. <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/credit-ratings-personality-inventure>
- Borio, C., Claessens, S., & Tarashev, N. (2022, August 3). *Entity-Based vs Activity-Based Regulation: A Framework and Applications to Traditional Financial Firms and Big Techs*. <https://www.bis.org/fsi/fsipapers19.htm>
- Bowmans. (2022, September 6). *Kenya: Court Extends the Application of the In Duplum Rule Non-bank Lending Businesses*. <https://bowmanslaw.com/insights/finance/kenya-court-extends-the-application-of-the-in-duplum-rule-non-bank-lending-businesses/>
- Business Daily Africa. (2016, October 29). *Competition Watchdog orders mobile cash firms to reveal faces*. <https://www.businessdailyafrica.com/news/CA-orders-mobile-cash-firms-to-reveal-fees/539546-3434244-6qmjew/index.html>
- Business Daily Africa. (2018, March 21). *M-Shwari fees are legal, court rules in Cofek case*. <https://www.businessdailyafrica.com/bd/corporate/companies/m-shwari-fees-are-legal-court-rules-in-cofek-case-2194816>
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2013). *The Banking Act, The Microfinance Act, Credit Reference Bureau Regulations 2013*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/CREDIT_REFERENCE_BUREAU_REGULATIONS_2013.pdf
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2016, September 13). *Banking Circular No. 4 of 2016*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/banking_circulars/1456582762_Banking%20Circular%20No%204%20of%202016%20-%20The%20Banking%20Amendment%20Act%202016.pdf

Central Bank of Kenya. (2018, July 11). *Fraudulent Financial Services, Products and Applications*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/press_releases/130503108_Public%20Notice%20-%20Fraudulent%20Financial%20Services%20Products%20and%20Applications.pdf

Central Bank of Kenya. (2019, April). 2019 FinAccess Household Survey. [https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/financial_inclusion/1035460079_2019%20FinAcces%20Report%20\(web\).pdf](https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/financial_inclusion/1035460079_2019%20FinAcces%20Report%20(web).pdf)

Central Bank of Kenya. (2020). *The Banking Act*. <https://www.centralbank.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Credit-Reference-Bureau-Regulations-2020.pdf>

Central Bank of Kenya (2020, April 14). *Publication of the Credit Reference Bureau Regulations, 2020 and Additional Measures on Credit Information Sharing*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/press_releases/850440997_Press%20Release%20-%20Credit%20Reference%20Bureau%20Regulations%20-%20April%202020.pdf

Central Bank of Kenya. (2021, November 8). *Suspension of the Listing of Negative Credit Information for Borrowers*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/press_releases/566112348_Press%20Release%20-%20Suspension%20of%20The%20Listing%20of%20Negative%20Credit%20Information%20for%20Borrowers.pdf

Central Bank of Kenya. (2022, March 18). *The Central Bank of Kenya (Digital Credit Providers) Regulations , 2022*. <https://www.centralbank.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/L.-N.-No.-46-Central-Bank-of-Kenya-Digital-Credit-Providers-Regulations-2022.pdf>

Central Bank of Kenya. (2022, November 14). *Credit Repair Framework*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/press_releases/318500544_Press%20Release%20-%20Credit%20Repair%20Framework.pdf

Central Bank of Kenya. (2023, March 27). *Licensing of Digital Credit Providers*. https://www.centralbank.go.ke/uploads/press_releases/927230_Press%20Release%20-%20Licensing%20of%20Digital%20Credit%20Providers%20March%202023.pdf

CM Advocates LLP. (2023, January 31). *Google Set to Ban Unlicensed Mobile Loan Apps on Play Store in New Developer Program Policy*. <https://cmadvocates.com/blog/google-set-to-ban-unlicensed-mobile-loan-apps-on-play-store-in-new-developer-program-policy>

Communications Authority of Kenya. (2022). *Second Quarter Sector Statistics Report for the Financial Year 2022/2023*. <https://www.ca.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Sector-Statistics-Report-Q2-2022-2023.pdf>

Competition Authority of Kenya. (2016, July 18). *Competition inquiry into USSD service provision in Kenya*. <https://cak.go.ke/sites/default/files/USSD%20Service%20Provision%20Market%20Inquiry.pdf>

Competition Authority of Kenya. (2017, June 30). *Competition and consumer protection in the Kenyan Banking sector*. <https://cak.go.ke/sites/default/files/Banking%20Sector%20Phase%20II%20Market%20Inquiry.pdf>

Cook, T., & McKay, C. (2015). *How M-Shwari Works: The story so far*. CGAP & FSD Kenya

Cost of Credit. (2013). *CBK Prudential Guidelines 2013: Guidelines on Consumer Protection*. <https://www.centralbank.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/PRUDENTIAL-GUIDELINES.pdf>

Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya. (2019, January 29). *Data Specification Template*. <https://ciskenya.co.ke/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Data-Specification-Template-V4.1.0-20190822.pdf>

Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya. (2021, May 18). *Code of Conduct for Third Party Credit Information Providers*. <https://ciskenya.co.ke/wp-content/files/2021/05/Code-of-Conduct-2021-Final-as-Approved.pdf>

di Castri, S., & Plaitakis, A. (2017, October 25). *Going Beyond Regulatory Sandboxes to Enable FinTech Innovation in Emerging Markets*. SSRN. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3059309

Financial Fortune Media. (2019, June 6). *Digital Money Lenders Form Association to Promote Fintech Industry*. <https://www.financialfortunemedia.com/fintech-firms-unveil-association-to-promote-digital-credit-growth/>

FSD Kenya. (2020, January). *2019 FinAccess Household Survey*. <https://www.fsdkenya.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/2019-FinAcces-Report-Web-05-JAN-2020.pdf>

FSD Kenya. (2021). *FinAccess 2021*. <https://www.fsdkenya.org/category/finaccess/finaccess-household-surveys/finaccess-2021/>

Fu, J., & Mishra, M. (2022, February 10). *Combating fraudulent and predatory fintech apps with machine learning*. Working paper. <https://poverty-action.org/sites/default/files/2023-05/Combating-Fraudulent-and-Predatory-Fintech-Apps-with-Machine-Learning-Policy-Brief-Fu-Mishra-Feb-2022-for-Project-Page.pdf>

Garz, S., Gine, X., Karlan, D., Mazer, R., Sanford, C., & Zinman, J. (2021, April). *Consumer Protection for Financial Inclusion in Low and Middle Income Countries: Bridging Regulator and Academic Perspectives*. *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, vol 13(1), pages 219-246.

Gubbins, P. (2019, December). *Digital Credit in Kenya: Facts and Figures from FinAccess 2019*. FSD Kenya.

Gubbins, P., & Heyer, A. (2022). *The State of Financial Health in Kenya: Evidence from FinAcces*. FSD Kenya.

Guguyu, O. (2018). *Blow for borrowers as court retains M-Shwari facilitation charges*. *The Standard*. <https://www.standardmedia.co.ke/article/2001274023/blow-for-borrowers-as-court-retains-m-shwari-charges?fbclid=IwAR21b9NKBGppLzcCqx-GxHw2-7XNhT9QrL2Z-a40mAtcaWAFwjOJY5nySSI>

Gwer, F., Odero, J., & Totolo, E. (2019, September). *Digital credit audit report: Evaluating the conduct and practice of digital lending in Kenya*. FSD Kenya. <https://www.fsdkenya.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/19-09-10-Regulation-Digital-credit-audit.pdf>

Herbling, D., & Genga, B. (2018, June 14). *Kenya Will Repeal Interest-Rate Cap That Curbed Bank Lending*. *Bloomberg*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-06-14/kenya-to-repeal-section-of-banking-law-that-caps-interest-rates#xj4y7vzkg>

Hustler Fund. (n.d.). The Financial Inclusion Fund. <https://hustlerfund.go.ke/>

Innovations for Poverty Action and Center for Effective Global Action. (Forthcoming). *Mobile Instant Credit: Impacts, Challenges and Lessons for Consumer Protection*.

Kenya Law. (2018). The Banking (Credit Reference Bureau) Regulations 2008. http://www.kenyalaw.org/kl/fileadmin/pdfdownloads/LegalNotices/2008/97-BankingAct_CreditReferenceBureau_Regulations_2008.pdf

Kenya Moja. (2022, December 6). *Brand New Start-Up Fund | Kenya to Introduce New Startup Bill in 2023*. <https://www.kenyamoja.com/video/brand-new-start-fund-kenya-introduce-new-startup-bill-2023-kbc-video-266391>

Kenyan Wall Street. (2018, May 30). *Financial Markets Conduct Bill 2018 a threat to CBK — Governor Njoroge*. <https://kenyanwallstreet.com/financial-markets-conduct-bill-2018-a-threat-to-cbk-governor-njoroge/>

Kihui, C. (2022, October 2). *Ban Whitepath Limited/Skypesa/Instarcash/Zuricash*. Change.org. https://www.change.org/p/ban-whitepath-limited-skypesa-instarcash-zuricash?recruiter=1256570802&recruited_by_id=e7f09d30-9e54-11ec-bcc5-1b8a1b7a1aa1&share_bandit_exp=initial-34586873-en-GB

Kiriori, N. (2023, April 12). *'Digital lender formed a WhatsApp group of my family over Sh25,000 debt'*. Nation Africa.

Kiruga, M. (2020, May 26). *This lending app publicly shames you when you're late on loan payment*. Rest of World. <https://restofworld.org/2020/okash-microlending-public-shaming/>

Kinyanjui, M. (2023, April 12). *Hustler Fund update: Kenyans have borrowed Sh26 billion*. The Star. <https://www.the-star.co.ke/news/2023-04-12-hustler-fund-update-kenyans-have-borrowed-sh26-billion/>

Mazer, R. (2023, April). *Moving markets towards open finance: Policy considerations for emerging markets and developing economies*. Raidiam. <https://raidiam.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Moving-Markets-Toward-Open-Finance.pdf>

Mazer, R., & Rowan, P. (2016, January). *Competition in Mobile Financial Services: Lessons from Kenya & Tanzania*. CGAP. <http://www.cgap.org/publications/competition-mobile-financial-services-lessons-kenya-tanzania>

Mazer, R., & McKee, K. (2017, August). *Consumer Protection in Digital Credit*. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/research/publication/consumer-protection-in-digital-credit> Mazer, R. (2016, February 2). *Competition & Mobile Financial Services: Move Past "Test & Learn"*. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/blog/competition-mobile-financial-services-move-past-test-learn>

Mazer, R. (2016, November 2). *Kenya Ends Hidden Costs for Digital Financial Services*. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/blog/kenya-ends-hidden-costs-for-digital-financial-services>

- Mazer, R. (2018, April 4). *Kenya's Rules on Mobile Money Price Transparency Are Paying Off*. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/blog/kenyas-rules-on-mobile-money-price-transparency-are-paying>
- Mazer, R. (2018b, June). *Emerging Data Sharing Models to Promote Financial Sector Innovation*. FSD Kenya. <https://www.fsdkenya.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Archive%20data%20FSD/Emerging-Data-Sharing-Models-to-Promote-Financial-Service-Innovation-June-2018-Mazer.pdf?t=1611045224>
- Mazer, R. (2021, September 30). *Digital Credit and Donor Funds: Public Goods for Private Companies?* Innovations for Poverty Action. <https://poverty-action.org/digital-credit-and-donor-funds-public-goods-private-companies>
- Mbego, S. (2019, June 28). *App lenders sign code of conduct, commit to responsible lending practices*. The Standard. <https://www.standardmedia.co.ke/business/business/article/2001331814/app-lenders-sign-code-of-conduct-commit-to-responsible-lending-practices>
- Muiruri, K. (2023, February 13). *CBK Licensing Unlocks Funding Nightmare for Digital Lenders*. Business Daily. <https://www.businessdailyafrica.com/bd/economy/cbk-licensing-unlocks-funding-nightmare-digital-lenders-4122624>
- Mukere, T. (2022, November 14). *CBK Rescues Kenyans Listed on CRB over 30-Day Loans*. <https://www.money254.co.ke/post/cbk-rescues-kenyans-listed-on-crb-over-30-day-loans-news>
- Mustafa, Z., Wachira, M., Bersudskaya, V., Nanjero, W., & Wright, G. (2017, March 22). *Where Credit is Due: Customer experience of digital credit in Kenya*. MicroSave Consulting.
- Muthiora, B. (2015, January). *Enabling Mobile Money Policies in Kenya: Fostering a Digital Financial Revolution*. GSMA. https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/dfs/Documents/2015_MMU_Enabling-Mobile-Money-Policies-in-Kenya.pdf
- National Council for Law Reporting with the Authority of the Attorney-General. (2011). *The National Payment Systems Act*. The Central Bank of Kenya. [https://www.centralbank.go.ke/images/docs/legislation/NATIONAL%20PAYMENT%20SYSTEM%20ACT%20\(No%2039%20of%202011\)%20\(2\).pdf](https://www.centralbank.go.ke/images/docs/legislation/NATIONAL%20PAYMENT%20SYSTEM%20ACT%20(No%2039%20of%202011)%20(2).pdf)
- Nderi, S. (2022, September 19). *CBK announces that only 10 digital loan companies have been licensed*. Hapa Kenya. <https://hapakenya.com/2022/09/19/cbk-announces-that-only-10-digital-loan-companies-have-been-licensed/>
- Njanja, A. (2023, March 24). *Google removes hundreds of Kenya-focused loan apps from Play Store*. TechCrunch. <https://techcrunch.com/2023/03/24/google-removes-hundreds-of-kenya-focused-loan-apps-from-play-store/?guccounter=1>
- Nkhonjera, M. (2017, April 12). *Competition Authority of Kenya (CAK) Rules on USSD Pricing*. Centre for Competition, Regulation and Economic Development. <https://www.competition.org.za/ccred-blog-competition-review/2017/4/12/competition-authority-of-kenya-cak-rules-on-ussd-pricing>

Office of the Data Protection Commissioner in Kenya. (2019). *Kenya Gazette Supplement: The Data Protection Act, 2019*. <https://www.odpc.go.ke/download/kenya-gazette-data-protection-act-2019/?wpdmdl=3235&refresh=648cb2301e8601686942256>

Ombija, S., & Chege, P. (2016, October 24). *Time to Take Data Privacy Concerns Seriously in Digital Lending*. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/blog/time-to-take-data-privacy-concerns-seriously-in-digital-lending>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2020, December 3). *Global Forum on Competition: Abuse of Dominance in Digital Markets*. [https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/GF/WD\(2020\)39/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP/GF/WD(2020)39/en/pdf)

Owino, J. (2019, May 21). *CBK Partners With Five Banks To Support SMEs*. Capital Business. <https://www.capitalfm.co.ke/business/2019/05/cbk-partners-with-five-banks-to-support-smes/>

Putman, D., Mazer, R., & Blackmon, W. (2021, May). *Report on the Competition Authority of Kenya Digital Credit Market Inquiry*. Competition Authority of Kenya and Innovations for Poverty Action. https://cak.go.ke/sites/default/files/Digital_Credit_Market_Inquiry_Report_2021.pdf

Reuters. (2021, December 7). *Kenya's president signs law change to regulate digital lenders*. <https://www.reuters.com/markets/rates-bonds/kenyas-president-signs-law-change-regulate-digital-lenders-2021-12-07/>

Reuters Staff. (2022, November 30). *Kenya's Ruto launches 'hustler fund' small loan scheme*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/article/kenya-economy/kenyas-ruto-launches-hustler-fund-small-loan-scheme-idUKL4N32Q3U5>

Robinson, J., Park, D., & Blumenstock, J. (2022, March 15). *The Impact of Digital Credit in Developing Economies: A Review of Recent Evidence*. Center for Effective Global Action, University of California Berkeley.

Safaricom. (n.d.). *KCB M-PESA loan disbursements cross KSh10B mark*. <https://www.safaricom.co.ke/media-center-landing/press-releases/kcb-m-pesa-loan-disbursements-cross-ksh10b-mark>

Safaricom. (n.d.b). *M-Shwari Terms & Conditions*. <https://www.safaricom.co.ke/media-center-landing/terms-and-conditions/m-shwari-terms-conditions>

Safaricom. (n.d.c). *Fuliza Terms & Conditions*. <https://www.safaricom.co.ke/media-center-landing/terms-and-conditions/fuliza-terms-and-conditions>

Safaricom. (2019, March 6). *Fuliza Demystified*. <https://newsroom.safaricom.co.ke/fuliza-demystified/>

Shorland, J. (2023, April 14). *More than a billion people depend on USSD-based services that fail at an alarming rate*. Medium. <https://medium.com/use-hover/more-than-a-billion-people-depend-on-ussd-based-services-that-fail-at-an-alarming-rate-63a992ba1a92>

Syminvest. (2014, May). *Kenya's Equity Bank Unveils MVNO Strategy, Launch Set for July*. <https://syminvest.com/news/kenyas-equity-bank-unveils-mvno-strategy-launch-set-for-july/2014/5/26/4336>

Tarazi, M. (2010, February 10). Branchless Banking: The Test and See Approach. CGAP. <https://www.cgap.org/blog/branchless-banking-test-and-see-approach>

The National Treasury of Kenya. (2016). *Draft Financial Services Authority Bill, 2016*. <https://www.treasury.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Financial-Services-Authority-Bill-2016.pdf>

The National Treasury of Kenya. (2018). *The Financial Markets Conduct Bill, 2018*. <https://www.treasury.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Draft-Financial-Markets-Conduct-Bill-2018.pdf>

Telecompaper. (2014, December 19). *Kenya court blocks thin SIM technology roll-out*. <https://www.telecompaper.com/news/kenya-court-blocks-thin-sim-technology-roll-out—1056162>

Vodafone. (2017, February 21). *M-Pesa, Africa's leading financial platform, marks 10th anniversary*. <https://www.vodafone.com/news/digital-society/m-pesa-10>

World Bank Group. (n.d.). *World Bank national accounts data and OECD National Accounts data files*. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?locations=KE>

World Bank Group. (2017). *Global Financial Inclusion and Consumer Protection Survey, 2017 Report*. World Bank, Washington, DC. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/28998> License: [CC BY 3.0 IGO](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

Abbreviations

CAK	Competition Authority of Kenya
CBK	Central Bank of Kenya
CRB	Credit Reference Bureau
CIS-K	Credit Information Sharing Association of Kenya
DLAK	Digital Lenders Association of Kenya
FSDK	Financial Sector Deepening Kenya
KCB	Kenya Commercial Bank